

To Evaluate The Pharmacological Activity Of ‘*Bryophyllum Pinnatum*’ On Ethylene Glycol Induce Urolithiasis In Rats.

Roushan Bhaskar^{1*}, Ajeet Pal Singh², Amar Pal Singh³

^{1*}Research Scholar, St. Soldier Institute of Pharmacy, Lidhran Campus, Behind NIT(R.E.C.), Jalandhar-Amritsar bypass NH-1 jalandhar-144011, Punjab, India.

²Dean Academic & HOD, St. Soldier Institute of Pharmacy, Jalandhar-144011, Punjab, India

³Principal, St. Soldier Institute of Pharmacy, Lidhran Campus, Behind NIT(R.E.C.), Jalandhar-Amritsar bypass NH-1 jalandhar-144011, Punjab, India.

ABSTRACT

Kidney stone (KS) is the most common disease on a global scale. It is also referred to as renal calculi, nephrolithiasis and urolithiasis. KS have a complicated pathogenesis that involves a number of metabolic and environmental alterations. Kidney stones can form from a variety of reasons, including hypercalciuria, hypocitraturia, hyperuricosuria, cystinuria hyperoxaluria, hyperparathyroidism, urinary tract infections, and renal tubular acidosis. The development of stones in the urinary tract is the outcome of the processes of crystal nucleation, aggregation, and retention in the urinary tract. Herbs used in traditional medicine have proven effective in treating it. The Herbal treatments contain several phytoconstituent and exert their beneficial results with the aid of a couple of mechanisms like:By targeting urine volume, pH, and Diuretic activity to enables in spontaneous passage of the stones. Via means of balancing the procedure of Inhibition and promoting of the crystallization in urine. With improving renal function and regulation of oxalate metabolism. Aim: The current study sought to assess the antiurolithiatic activity of the ethanolic extract of ‘*Bryophyllum pinnatum*’ leaves in rats suffering from ethylene-glycol-induced urolithiasis. Methods: For the purpose of evaluating the antiurolithiatic activity of the ethanolic extract of ‘*Bryophyllum pinnatum*’ leaves, 30 Female rats were chosen. The trial lasted for almost one month. There were 5 groups of animals, each with 6 rats. An ethylene glycol-induced urolithiasis model was used for the study. Cystone (500mg/kg) was used as a standard drug. The herbal extract was prepared freshly. The animals were treated with prepared extract of ‘*Bryophyllum pinnatum*’ leaves plant. Renal deposits and chronic Crystalluria were eventually discovered at day 14. Treatment is provided to group III through group V from day 15 to day 28. Biochemical measurements (urine and serum analysis) and behavioral parameters (body weight analysis and water intake capacity) were routinely carried out. Animals are sacrificed on day 28, and the findings are assessed using kidney homogenate and histology. Volume of urine, Serum creatinine, uric acid, and blood urea nitrogen levels were checked for calcium, magnesium, and other functional and damage markers. Result: As a result, ‘*Bryophyllum pinnatum*’ leaves extract, is secure and has a healing effect. Oxalate, calcium, and phosphate excretion were increased in hypercalculi animals. However, the calculogenic rat's enhanced kidney stone-forming ingredient deposition was dramatically reduced. The herbal ethanolic extract of ‘*Bryophyllum pinnatum*’ leaves has been found to have a strong antiurolithiatic effect. Conclusion: The findings of this investigation point to the potential value of herbal ethanolic extract of ‘*Bryophyllum pinnatum*’ leaves as an effective antiurolithiatic medication.

Keywords: Kidney stones, *Bryophyllum pinnatum*, Herbal drugs, ethylene-glycol-induced urolithiasis.

INTRODUCTION

Urinary stone disease, commonly known as urolithiasis, is a major health problem affecting people worldwide. It is often associated with severe and sudden lower back pain, and in more serious cases, it can lead to complications such as

pyelonephritis and acute renal failure, emphasizing its clinical importance¹. The condition has a global prevalence of about 3–5% annually, while lifetime prevalence is estimated to range between 15% and 25%. Recurrence is a key challenge in urolithiasis, with nearly 10% of patients experiencing recurrence

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within the first year, 50% within 5–10 years, and up to 75% over a 20-year period, indicating its chronic and relapsing nature².

Kidney stones vary widely in size and may occur as single or multiple formations. They are broadly classified into calcium stones and non-calcium stones, including uric acid, struvite, and cystine stones. Among these, calcium stones are the most prevalent worldwide. The incidence of stone formation is significantly higher in males compared to females, which may be attributed to the promoting effect of testosterone and the protective role of estrogen in stone formation³.

The formation of kidney stones is strongly influenced by urinary constituents such as calcium, magnesium, and citrate. Approximately 85% of renal stones consist of calcium, mainly in the form of calcium oxalate or calcium phosphate. In contrast, magnesium and citrate act as natural inhibitors of stone formation⁴. The development of calcium stones involves several sequential steps, including nucleation, crystal growth, aggregation, and retention within the renal tubules⁵.

Various endogenous substances can either promote or inhibit stone formation. Factors such as low urine volume, acidic pH, and elevated levels of calcium, sodium, oxalate, and uric acid increase the risk of stone development. On the other hand, inhibitors like citrate, magnesium, and certain proteins such as nephrocalcin, prothrombin fragment 1, and osteopontin help prevent crystal formation and aggregation⁶.

Management of nephrolithiasis depends on the size, type, and location of the stone. Acute treatment focuses on relieving pain, managing urinary obstruction, and stabilizing the patient, while long-term management aims at preventing recurrence and controlling risk factors⁷. Advances in medical technology have shifted treatment approaches from invasive surgical procedures to minimally invasive techniques, improving patient outcomes and quality of life. Preventive strategies include lifestyle modifications, dietary management, and appropriate pharmacological interventions⁸.

Medical Expulsion Therapy (MET) has gained popularity for the management of small and uncomplicated stones. It enhances the spontaneous passage of stones and reduces the time required for expulsion. The success of MET largely depends on stone size—stones smaller than 4 mm are usually passed easily, while those between 4–6 mm have a moderate expulsion rate, and stones larger than 8 mm rarely pass without intervention. In such cases, procedures like ureteroscopy (URS), extracorporeal shockwave lithotripsy (ESWL), and percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PCNL) are recommended. Therefore, accurate assessment of stone characteristics is essential for selecting the appropriate treatment strategy⁹.

In recent years, there has been growing interest in the use of medicinal plants for the management of kidney stones. These natural therapies contain a wide range of bioactive compounds that contribute to their therapeutic effects. Herbal remedies may help in increasing urine output, modifying urinary pH, and promoting diuretic activity, thereby facilitating stone passage. Additionally, they play a role in regulating crystal formation processes and improving overall kidney function, particularly by influencing oxalate metabolism^{10,11}.

1. AIM & OBJECTIVE

1.1 Aim of the study:

The present study is aimed to evaluate the Antiuro lithiatic activity of ethanolic extract of '*Bryophyllum pinnatum*' leaves in Ethylene-glycol induced Urolithiasis in rats.

1.2 Objective of the study:

- (i) Induction of kidney stones in experimental animal using Ethylene-glycol Urolithiatic model.
- (ii) Extraction of the ethanolic extract of '*Bryophyllum pinnatum*' leaves to make the test drug preparation.
- (iii) To evaluate the Antilithiatic activity of ethanolic extract of '*Bryophyllum pinnatum*'

leaves in Ethylene-glycol induced Urolithiatic model.

- (iv) To determine the effect of the extract against urolithiasis.
- (v) Perform Behaviour parameters, Biochemical parameters, Histopathology and Kidney homogenate test for evaluation of results.

1.3 Scope of the study:

- The present study was conducted to evaluate the antilithiatic activity of the ethanolic extract of 'Bryophyllum pinnatum' leaves. Kidney stone disease is a complex and multifactorial disorder with a high recurrence rate despite allopathic treatment. Herbal therapies contain various phytoconstituents and produce beneficial effects through multiple mechanisms. By targeting urine volume, pH and Diuretic activity to enable the spontaneous passage of the stones.
- Via means of balancing the procedure of Inhibition and promoting of the crystallization in urine.
- With improving renal function and regulation of oxalate metabolism¹².
- By use of ethanolic extract of 'Bryophyllum pinnatum' leaves, preventing urinary infection and also exerting antiurolithiatic activity¹³.
- By inhibiting oxidation and further renal cell injury, the ethanolic extract of 'Bryophyllum pinnatum' leaves^{14,15}.
- By use of ethanolic extract of 'Bryophyllum pinnatum' leaves preventing stone growth and also exerts antilithiatic activity^{16,17}.
- The phytochemical profile of the plant has suggested it to be an effective antiurolithiatic preparation but no such scientifically carried out study was available yet, which prompted us to explore the effect of this preparation on urolithiasis.

- The ethanolic extract of 'Bryophyllum pinnatum' leaves herbal extract is used to target multiple steps of stone formation and to exert effect of herbal drugs for better treatment of disease and success rate of therapy¹⁸.

2. MATERIAL & METHOD

3.1 Material Requirement:

3.1.1 Chemicals and equipment requirements:

Ethylene glycol and all other chemicals and reagents used were analytical grade and procured from approved chemical suppliers. Apparatus such as the metabolic cages, homogenizer, were used in the study.

3.1.2 Plant Material:

The plants ethanolic extract of 'Bryophyllum pinnatum' leaves were purchased and COA provided by Kshipra Biotech.

3.2 Methodology:

• Standard drug:

Cystone tablet 500 mg/kg is used as a standard drug.

• Test component:

Ethanolic extract of 'Bryophyllum pinnatum' leaves was used as the test component.

3.3 Procurement of animals:

Healthy male Wistar albino rats, weighing 140–200 g, were procured from the AHF, Lovely Professional University, Jalandhar, and housed in the Animal House Facility of St. Soldier Institute of Pharmacy, Jalandhar, Punjab, India. The animals were kept in polypropylene cages under standard laboratory conditions, including a 12-hour light–dark cycle, temperature of $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, and relative humidity of $60 \pm 5\%$. They were provided with a standard pellet diet and water ad libitum¹⁹.

3.4 Experimental protocol:

3.4.1 Induction of Disease:

The ethylene glycol (EG)-induced hyperoxaluria model was used in this study. EG is a well-established lithogenic agent in rodent models. A 0.75% concentration of EG was added to the drinking water and administered to rats in groups II through V for 28 days. Crystalluria typically develops within 12 days, while renal crystal deposits appear within 3 weeks. Administration of EG leads to the induction of hyperoxaluria, crystalluria, and calcium oxalate nephrolithiasis²⁰.

3.4.2 Experimental Design:

Wistar albino rats weighing between 140 and 200 g were used for the study. The animals were housed in polypropylene cages and maintained under standard laboratory conditions, including a 12-hour light/dark cycle, a temperature of $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, and a relative humidity of $60 \pm 5\%$. They were provided with a standard pellet diet and water ad libitum¹⁹.

The rats were divided into five groups, with six animals in each group:

- **Group I (Control group):** Received regular food and drinking water for 28 days.
- **Group II (Negative control group):** Treated with ethylene glycol (EG) only for 28 days to induce the disease model.
- **Group III (Standard group):** Treated with EG for 28 days and received the antiurolithiatic drug Cystone (500 mg/kg) from day 15 to 28.
- **Group IV (Treatment group 1):** Treated with EG for 28 days and received ethanolic extract of *Bryophyllum pinnatum* leaves (250 mg/kg) from day 15 to 28.
- **Group V (Treatment group 2):** Treated with EG for 28 days and received ethanolic extract of *Bryophyllum pinnatum* leaves (500 mg/kg) from day 15 to 28.

Table 5: Grouping of animals:

S. NO.	GROUPS	STUDY DESIGN	TREATMENT	DOSE (mg/kg)	DAYS
1.	Group I	Solvent control	Vehicle only	-	28
2.	Group II	Positive control group	Ethylene glycol (EG)	0.75%	28
3.	Group III	Standard drug treatment	Cystone+ EG	500 +0.75%	15 - 28
4.	Group IV	<i>Bryophyllum pinnatum</i> extract	<i>Bryophyllum pinnatum</i> extract + EG	250mg/kg+0.75%	15 - 28
5.	Group V	<i>Bryophyllum pinnatum</i> extract	<i>Bryophyllum pinnatum</i> extract +EG	500mg/kg+0.75%	15 - 28

Dosing:

1. Ethylene glycol (EG)-0.75

2. Cystone-500mg/kg

3Ethanolic extract of '*Bryophyllum pinnatum*' leaves -250mg/kg and 500mg/kg

Total No. of animals required:

No.of the animal in each group (n) = 06

No. of groups (N) = 05

Treatment Schedule and Study Design in In Vivo Studies. A total of 30 female rats were used to evaluate the antilithiatic activity of the herbal preparation. The study was conducted for approximately one month, and the animals were allowed to acclimatize for one week before the

experiment. The rats were divided into five groups, each consisting of six animals. An ethylene glycol–induced urolithiasis model was used, which produced persistent crystalluria by day 12 and renal crystal deposition by the third week. Treatment was administered from the 15th to the 28th day to groups

II to V. Behavioral parameters and biochemical parameters, including urine and serum analysis, were monitored regularly. On the 28th day, the animals were sacrificed, and further biochemical evaluations were carried out.

3.6 Various Test and procedures to be performed in In Vivo Studies in detail:

3.6.1 Behaviour parameters-

- **Body weight analysis (%):** Body weight should be monitored regularly in each group of animals. At the end of the study, changes in body weight for each group should be recorded²¹.
- **Water intake analysis:** The 24-hour water intake of each group should be measured regularly. Changes in water consumption should be determined for each group at the end of the study²¹.

3.6.2 Biochemical parameters-

- **Urine analysis:** Urine samples will be collected after dosing by placing animals in metabolic cages, where they have free access to water. The collected urine will be analyzed for calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, urine volume, and urine pH. At the end of the study, changes in these parameters will be determined for each group of animals^{19,22}.
Purpose: To compare alterations in calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, urine volume, and urine pH among control, disease, and treatment groups.
- **Serum analysis:** Blood samples will be collected from each group via retro-orbital puncture. The samples will be centrifuged at 3000 rpm at 20°C for 15 minutes to obtain serum, which will be analyzed for calcium, phosphorus, blood urea nitrogen, uric acid, urea, and creatinine. Differences in these parameters will be determined at the end of the study for each group¹⁹.
Purpose: To evaluate changes in serum biochemical markers across control, disease, and treatment groups.

- **Histopathology:** For histopathological examination, rats will be sacrificed, and their kidneys will be removed and weighed. The kidneys will be washed with 0.15 M KCl, stored in 10% buffered formalin, fixed in Bouin's solution, embedded in paraffin, and sectioned at 2–3 µm intervals. The sections will be stained with hematoxylin and eosin and examined under a polarized light microscope, with photographs taken for documentation^{21,23}.
Purpose: To assess structural changes in renal tissue, including renal injury, glomerular shrinkage, and necrosis in the cortex and medulla in disease and treated groups¹⁷.
- **Kidney homogenate:** Renal tissue will be excised, weighed, and cut into small pieces. A 10% (w/v) homogenate will be prepared in 0.1 M PBS buffer (pH 7.4). The homogenate will be analyzed for magnesium, phosphate, calcium, acid phosphatase (ACP), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), and lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) levels^{21,22}.

4 RESULT & DISCUSSION

4.1 Changes in body weight and water intake capacity:

Changes in body weight and water intake were recorded by measuring the weight of the animals on the first and last days of treatment and calculating the percentage change. Water intake was measured over 24 h and expressed as grams per day.

Group I (control) showed no significant changes in body weight or water intake. In contrast, Group II showed a decrease in body weight and a significant increase in water intake. Groups III–V showed a significant increase in body weight. Water intake remained similar in all groups except Group II, where it was significantly higher than that in the control group (Table 14).

Figure 14: Rat placed on weighing balance.

Table 6: Change in Body Weight in different groups of animals.

S.No.	Groups	Change in body weight (%)	Changes in Water intake capacity (ml/24h)
1.	Group I	13.87±0.34	6.16±0.08
2.	Group II	2.66±0.02**a	12.95±0.02**a
3.	Group III	6.75±0.008**ab	8.76±0.008**ab
4.	Group IV	3.55±0.02**ab	7.88±0.06**ab
5.	Group V	4.24±0.02**ab	10.45±0.06**ab

Values for urine parameters are measured in 24 h urine sample. All values are stated as mean±SEM

(n=6). a Comparisons are made with Group I, b Comparisons are made with Group II, *P

4.2 Biochemical parameters

- Urine analysis:** All animals were kept in individual metabolic cages, and 24-hour urine samples were collected on the 28th day of the experiment. During this period, the animals had free access to drinking water. A drop of concentrated HCl was added to each urine sample before storing them at 4°C. The collected urine

samples were analyzed for the following parameters.

Figure 15: Rat placed in metabolic cage for urine sample

Table 16 shows the levels of phosphate, calcium, and magnesium in the urine samples of Groups I to V. In this study, male Wistar rats were administered 1% ethylene glycol in drinking water, which significantly increased the levels of phosphate and calcium and decreased magnesium levels in urine in Group II compared to the control group (Group I). However, treatment with Groups IV and V significantly reduced phosphate and calcium levels and increased magnesium levels in the urine. These effects were similar to those observed in the standard treatment group (Group III, treated with Cystone).

Table 7: Changes in Urinary Parameters in different groups of animals.

S.No.	Groups	Treatment	Urine parameters[mg/dl]				
			Calcium	Phosphorus	Magnesium	Urine volume	Urine pH
1.	Group-I	Control group	2.36±0.06	3.18±0.17	5.12±0.02	17.32±0.22	6.4±0.02
2.	Group-II	Disease group	4.33±0.05**a	7.06±0.18**a	1.22±0.02**a	10.64±0.16**a	8.6±0.02**a
3.	Group-III	Standard group	2.95±0.11**ab	4.22±0.11**ab	2.34±0.008**ab	15.94±0.32**ab	7.4±.16**ab
4.	Group-IV	Herbal preparation (low dose)	3.57±0.14**ab	5.93±0.24**ab	2.32±0.008**ab	18.18±0.72**ab	6.4±0.94**
5.	Group-V	Herbal preparation (high dose)	3.1±0.14b**ab	5.37±0.22**ab	2.52±0.014**ab	18.22±0.72**ab	6.6±0.96**ab

Values for urine parameters are measured in 24 h urine sample. All values are stated as mean±SEM (n=6). a Comparisons are made with Group I, b Comparisons are made with Group II, *P

- **Serum analysis:** Blood samples were collected from each group of animals using retro-orbital puncture. The samples were then centrifuged at 3000 rpm and 20°C for 15 min to separate the serum.
- Blood sample of each group of animals will collect from the retro orbital puncture. After that blood sample was centrifuged at 3000 rpm, 20°C for 15 minutes and analyze the serum calcium, phosphorus, urea and creatinine. At the end of the study determine the difference in each group of animals¹⁹.

Figure 16: Blood collection by Retro-Orbital Puncture

Serum calcium, phosphorus, urea, and creatinine levels in Group I–V were measured to assess the function of the kidneys. As a symptom of renal damage, Group II (the disease group) had considerably higher concentrations of calcium, phosphate, urea, and creatinine. Nevertheless, treatment groups exhibit a decline in calcium, phosphate, urea, and creatinine levels equivalent to the Standard group (Group III).

Table 8: Changes in Serum parameters in different groups of animals

S.No.	Groups	Treatment	Serum parameters[mg/dl]			
			Calcium	Phosphorus	Urea	Creatinine
1.	Group-I	Control group	8.26±0.06	8.07±0.02	13.74±0.01	0.36±0.02
2.	Group-II	Disease group	14.74±0.02**a	14.04±0.06**a	26.24±0.01**a	1.34±0.006**a
3.	Group-III	Standard group	12.24±0.02**ab	10.77±0.008**ab	16.79±0.03*8ab	0.84±0.03**ab
4.	Group-IV	Herbal preparation (low dose)	11.67±0.006**ab	11.06±0.008**ab	18.56±0.008**ab	0.87±0.004**ab
5.	Group-V	Herbal preparation (high dose)	12.05±0.008**ab	10.74±0.008**ab	17.74±0.02**ab	0.98±0.02**ab

Values for urine parameters are measured in 24 h urine sample. All values are stated as mean±SEM (n=6). a Comparisons are made with Group I, b Comparisons are made with Group II, *P

• Analysis of kidney histopathology:

Renal histopathology results showed that the control group (Group I) had normal kidney structure with no calcium oxalate (CaOx) crystal deposits or abnormalities in the kidney structure. In contrast, the disease group (Group II) showed many CaOx crystal deposits in the renal tubules, along with congestion

and blood vessels. The standard dilation treatment group (Group III) showed mostly normal kidney structure with slight tubular dilation, mild inflammation, and a few CaOx crystal deposits. In the treatment groups (Groups IV–VII), the kidneys showed nearly normal structure with only minor vacuolar changes and no CaOx crystal deposits (Figure 23).

Figure 17: Histopathology of sections of kidneys of various groups used for the study.

- **Analysis of Kidney homogenate analysis:** In the stone-induced group, the calcium and phosphate levels in the kidney tissue were significantly increased, whereas the magnesium levels were

decreased. However, in both the preventive and curative treatment groups, the herbal combination significantly reduced calcium and phosphate levels and increased magnesium levels to near normal, similar to the standard drug group.

Table 9: Changes in Kidney homogenate parameters in different groups of animals.

S.No.	Groups	Treatment	Kidney Homogenate Parameters		
			Calcium	Phosphorus	Magnesium
1.	Group-I	Control group	9.74±0.02	2.62±0.04	3.86±0.02
2.	Group-II	Disease group	16.76±0.02**a	7.76±0.02**a	0.84±0.006**a
3.	Group-III	Standard group	12.46±0.008**ab	3.11±0.02**ab	2.43±0.006**ab
4.	Group-IV	Herbal preparation (low dose)	12.37±0.004**ab	3.43±0.006**ab	2.32±0.008**ab
5.	Group-V	Herbal preparation (high dose)	12.77±0.004**ab	3.92±0.006**ab	2.44±0.006**ab

All values are stated as mean±SEM (n=6). a Comparisons are made with Group I, b Comparisons are made with Group II, *P

Histological studies showed that the treatment groups (Groups III–V) had normal kidney structures with no signs of injury or crystal deposition. These findings indicate that the herbal combination is effective in preventing and treating urolithiasis caused by ethylene glycol.

The herbal treatment may help prevent the recurrence of kidney stones by reducing the early stages of stone formation. Although the exact mechanism is not fully

understood, it may work by increasing urine output and decreasing the concentration of stone-forming substances in the urine.

5. CONCLUSION

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7. CONFLICTS OF INTERESTS

There are no conflicts of interest.

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